

A FINITE ELEMENT MODEL TO PREDICT MULTI-AXIAL STRESS-STRAIN RESPONSE OF CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES WITH STRAIN INDUCED DAMAGE

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SUMMARY

Strain induced damage modes and their interactions are modelled using the finite element method for CMC tows and $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ laminates. For both situations, bi-axial straining is addressed, together with the degradation of Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios. In all cases, the expected stress-strain behaviour is predicted.

Keywords: CMCs; Tows; Finite Element Method; Damage Mechanisms; Orthotropic Material; Constitutive Equations

INTRODUCTION

The superior material properties of Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMCs), e.g. low density and good mechanical and thermal properties at high temperatures make them favourable materials for use in: rocket nozzles; thermal protection systems; and gas turbine engines [1]. To perform optimal design of these engineering components, a highly efficient yet computational accurate model is a necessary requirement, due to the complex spatial topology and interactive damage mechanisms of woven CMCs.

A finite element (FE) model of a unit cell geometry is a commonly used approach to study the behaviour of CMCs. Sheikh *et al.* [2] employed a microstructural FE model to predict steady-state and transient heat conduction for the plain weave DLR-XT composite. Deepak and Whitcomb [3] evaluated load flow in plain weave composites by using a detailed 3D FE model and a non-standard post-processing technique. Although the full FE analysis is capable of predicting accurate micromechanical responses, it is computationally expensive because a precise description of the geometry is required.

In order to tackle practical problems in the design and analysis of composites, some computationally efficient FE models have been developed. Tanov and Tabiei [4] predicted the equivalent material properties of plain weave fabric composites by homogenising an entire unit cell model. Cox *et al.* [5] introduced a Binary Model, which is composed of two virtual components: a 1D truss element and a 3D solid element. Whilst the Binary Model has great simplicity, it does require accurate determination of the mechanical and thermal properties of the two virtual components.

However, an alternative simpler and more accurate approach has been adopted here. For all of these approaches, the material properties are assumed to be linear elastic.

The present paper addresses the development of a conceptually simple and computationally economic FE model, which emphasises the effects of strain-induced damage modes and their interactions on the mechanical behaviour. Non-linear material properties are modelled by multi-linear elastic discretisation. A uni-directional tow is homogenised to a single orthotropic block. Multi-axial stress-strain response and degradation of material properties are modelled for uni-directional tows and $0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminates.

Figure 1. Schematic drawings of (a) A uni-directional tow under longitudinal extension; (b) and (c) Longitudinal stress-strain and Poisson's ratio-strain curves; and (d)–(g) Corresponding damage modes.

Figure 2. Measured [8] and assumed variation of Poisson's ratios, v_{31} and v_{32} with longitudinal strain.

DAMAGE MODES AND MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF A UNI-DIRECTIONAL TOW

The damage modes and typical mechanical behaviour of a uni-directional tow subjected to different loading conditions are described in this section. The interactions of different damage modes and their effects on the stress-strain response are introduced.

Longitudinal extension

When a uni-directional fibre-reinforced ceramic matrix composite tow (single bundle of fibres and associated matrices) is under uniform extension along the fibre direction (Figure 1a), the typical longitudinal stress-strain response [5] (Figure 1b) and Poisson's ratio-longitudinal strain curve (Figure 1c), can be observed. The four characteristic stages in the stress-strain curve are now described [7]:

AB: initially, the composite behaves as a virgin, undamaged, linear elastic material;

BC: periodic matrix cracking occurs (Figure 1d);

CD: fibre-matrix interface debonding takes place at the matrix crack tip and its wake (wake debonding in Figure 1e); and weaker fibres fail (Figure 1f);

DE: the majority of fibres fail and are pulled out against the frictional stress along the wake debonding interface (Figure 1g).

Figure 2 shows how the Poisson's ratio-longitudinal strain curve in Figure 1c can be idealised from the experimental data [8] for a uni-directional Nicalon/CAS composite. It can be seen that initially, Poisson's ratio is constant, then decreases linearly due to matrix cracking and wake debonding, and finally approaches zero at peak stress D, as shown in Figure 1b.

Figure 3. Schematic drawings of (a) A uni-directional tow under transverse straining; (b) and (c) Transverse stress-strain and Poisson's ratio curves; and (d)–(f) Corresponding damage modes.

Figure 4. Schematic drawings of (a) A uni-directional tow under shear straining; (b) and (c) Shear stress-strain curve; and (c)–(e) Corresponding damage modes.

Transverse extension

When a uni-directional tow is subjected to transverse extension (Figure 3a), the material response is assumed to be piecewise linear elastic (Figure 3b and 3c). When the global transverse strain reaches a critical value, fibre-matrix debonding and/or matrix cracking (Figure 3d–3f) is assumed to take place which leads to catastrophic failure.

Shear loading

As can be seen from Figure 4, in the case of shear straining, the shear stress-strain response and damage modes are assumed to have the same form as those for transverse straining.

Figure 5. Schematic drawing of (a) No-pullout stress-strain curve; (b) Variation of the normalised number of wake debonded blocks with longitudinal strain.

Damage interactions and no-pullout curve

When a uni-directional tow is under multi-axial loading, e.g. both longitudinal and transverse straining (ϵ_{33} and ϵ_{22}); or both longitudinal and shear straining (ϵ_{33} and γ_{23}), the interaction between certain damage modes is strong and needs to be considered. The positive transverse stress (σ_{11}) or shear stress (τ_{23}) advances wake debonding, and hence decouples the interaction between fibres and matrix. As a result, the contribution due to fibre pullout has to be deactivated. Figure 5a shows that the original stress-strain curve degrades to the no-pullout curve due to this damage interaction [5]. The damage interaction results in the change of Poisson's ratios.

The broken curve in Figure 5b represents the variation of the normalised number of wake debonded blocks (fibre-matrix between adjacent matrix cracks) in a tow with longitudinal strain [7]. In the present model, it is assumed that all the blocks wake debond at the point, W, viz. the dash curve in Figure 5b is idealised to the solid curve. The strain level at which the deactivation point W occurs has been determined by examination of the original and no-pullout curves (Figure 5a). Consequently, Poisson's ratios ν_{31} and ν_{32} drop to zero at the wake debonding strain, ϵ_{33}^w , when the switch to the no-pullout curve is activated.

FORMULATION OF THE FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

A uni-directional tow is chosen to be the basic constituent in the FE model, and therefore an entire tow, which consists of thousands of fibres embedded in matrix, can be represented by a single 8-node solid finite element (Figure 6). The material properties are assumed to be multi-linear elastic and the stress-strain and Poisson's ratios-strain curves shown in Figures 1, 3 and 4 are used to develop the constitutive equations. The FE package ABAQUS [9] with a user-defined subroutine UMAT is used to carry out the simulation.

Figure 6. Homogenisation of a uni-directional tow to a single orthotropic block.

This method has the benefit of being able to model a tow by a single orthotropic finite element. The approach has the advantage of simplicity relative to the binary system of modelling [5], since it has only one component; and, unlike the binary method, does not suffer from the difficulties associated with the identification of medium properties.

Homogenisation of a uni-directional tow

A heterogeneous uni-directional tow is homogenised to a single block (Figure 6), which has the same overall dimensions and equivalent orthotropic material properties. There are nine independent material properties:

Young's moduli: E_3 , E_2 , and E_1 ;

Poisson's ratios: ν_{31} , ν_{32} , and ν_{12} ;

Shear moduli: G_{12} , G_{23} , and G_{13} .

Discretisation of the stress-strain curve and constitutive equations

In order to perform a finite element analysis, the non-linear longitudinal stress-strain relationship is discretised to a multi-linear curve. The loading is imposed in terms of the displacement boundary conditions, i.e. displacement controlled rather than load controlled conditions are modelled. The applied displacement is divided into many small increments. For each increment, the constitutive equations for an orthotropic material are:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \tau_{23} \\ \tau_{13} \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1-\nu_{23}\nu_{32}}{E_2 E_3 \Delta} & \frac{\nu_{21} + \nu_{23}\nu_{31}}{E_2 E_3 \Delta} & \frac{\nu_{31} + \nu_{21}\nu_{32}}{E_2 E_3 \Delta} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{21} + \nu_{23}\nu_{31}}{E_2 E_3 \Delta} & \frac{1-\nu_{13}\nu_{31}}{E_1 E_3 \Delta} & \frac{\nu_{32} + \nu_{12}\nu_{31}}{E_1 E_3 \Delta} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{31} + \nu_{21}\nu_{32}}{E_2 E_3 \Delta} & \frac{\nu_{32} + \nu_{12}\nu_{31}}{E_1 E_3 \Delta} & \frac{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}}{E_1 E_2 \Delta} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{23} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{13} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{12} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{11} \\ \epsilon_{22} \\ \epsilon_{33} \\ \gamma_{23} \\ \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta = \frac{(1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}-\nu_{23}\nu_{32}-\nu_{13}\nu_{31}-2\nu_{21}\nu_{32}\nu_{13})}{E_1E_2E_3}$ and $\nu_{ij} = \frac{E_i}{E_j}\nu_{ji}$ ($i, j = 1-3$ and $i \neq j$).

Assumptions of mechanical couplings due to damage interactions

To model the interactions of the different damage modes, the following assumptions are made.

1. The switch from the original stress-strain curve to the no-pullout curve is triggered by a small finite positive transverse stress, or by a small non-zero shear stress in the 1-3 or 2-3 plane.
2. Consequently, the Poisson's ratios, ν_{31} and ν_{32} drop to zero at the wake debonding strain, ε_{33}^w (Figure 5).

UMAT implementation in ABAQUS

The present model is implemented by using the finite element package, ABAQUS/standard and a user defined subroutine, UMAT. The multi-linear material properties, the constitutive equations, and the mechanical couplings are defined in the UMAT. For every increment, the UMAT reads the strains at each material point and then assigns the corresponding Young's moduli, Poisson's ratios and shear moduli. The constitutive equations are then used to update the stress fields. Solution-dependent state variables, STATEV, record different damage modes and control their interactions. Automatic incrementation algorithms and increment redefinition variable, PNEWDT, are continuously updated to ensure that the discretised points are located exactly at the end of the relevant increments.

MULTI-AXIAL TOW AND 0°/90° LAMINATE BEHAVIOUR

Figure 7. Material properties of a uni-directional tow.

The current model is used to analyse a uni-directional tow and a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminate under different loading cases. Applications to composite woven unit cells and real engineering components will be pursued as future developments.

Material properties

The material properties of a uni-directional tow of C/C-SiC (Carbon/Carbon-Silicon Carbide) DLR-XT composite are shown in Figure 7. Figure 7a, which is associated with Figure 5a, has been obtained by using the model for a uni-directional tow [7]. The solid curve is the original longitudinal stress-strain relationship, the broken line defines the no-pullout curve, and the cross symbol is the wake debonding point. The initial values of other properties, transverse moduli (Figure 7b), Poisson's ratios (Figure 7c), and shear moduli (Figure 7d) have been calibrated by a fully meshed micro-mechanical FE model. The limit of proportionality of the experimental stress-strain curve for the DLR-XT material under uni-axial straining, is used to define a transverse failure strain of 0.04% [10]. A value of 26MPa is used to determine the critical shear failure strain [11].

Figure 8. Finite element results for a uni-directional tow under longitudinal straining (ϵ_{33}).

Figure 9. Finite element results for a uni-directional tow under transverse straining (ϵ_{33}).

Figure 10. Finite element results for a uni-directional tow under shear straining.

Uni-directional tow: longitudinal, transverse and shear straining

Figure 8 shows the FE results for a uni-directional tow under longitudinal straining. The stress-strain relationship, longitudinal-transverse strain curves, and variation of Poisson's ratios are plotted in Figure 8a, 8b, and 8c, respectively. As expected, the results are identical to the defined material properties. The results for a uni-directional tow subjected to transverse and shear straining are presented in Figures 9 and 10, respectively. Once again, the method has been validated since input and output values concur.

Figure 11. Finite element results for a uni-directional tow under equi-biaxial straining ($\epsilon_{33} = \epsilon_{11}$).

Figure 12. Finite element results for a uni-directional tow under longitudinal straining (ϵ_{33}) and shear straining (γ_{23}) with $\epsilon_{33} = \gamma_{23}$.

Uni-directional tow: equi-biaxial straining

Figure 11 shows the FE results for a tow under equi-biaxial tensile straining, $\epsilon_{33} = \epsilon_{11}$. From Figure 11a, it can be seen that the no-pullout stress-strain curve is triggered due to the positive stress σ_{11} . Figure 11b shows that the transverse stress, σ_{11} drops to zero at the defined failure strain ($\epsilon_{11} = 0.04\%$). The effect of this transverse failure on the deformation in the other transverse direction is shown as a kink in Figure 11c. The

effect can also be seen from the first sharp drop in Figure 11d, which plots the ratio of strains in Figure 11c. The second sharp drop in Figure 11d is due to the second assumption of mechanical coupling, namely that the Poisson's ratio drops to zero at the wake debonding strain.

Uni-directional tow: combined longitudinal and shear straining

In comparison with the predictions for equi-biaxial straining, similar results are obtained for longitudinal and shear straining (Figure 12). In this case, the switch from original to no-pullout curve is triggered by the shear stress. Transverse strains become zero at the wake debonding strain.

Figure 13. Schematic drawing of a 0°/90° tow laminate under uni-axial straining

Figure 14. Overall behaviour of a 0°/90° laminate under uni-axial straining .

Figure 15. Local behaviour of a 0°/90° laminate under uni-axial straining.

0°/90° laminate under uni-axial straining, $\varepsilon_{33}^{\infty}$

The model is also used to analyse a 0°/90° laminate under in-plane uni-axial straining (Figure 13). The overall stress-strain response and variations of transverse strains are shown in Figure 14a and 14b, respectively. The kinks at $\varepsilon_{33}^{\infty}=0.04\%$ in both figures are due to the matrix cracking in the 90° tows. The transverse strains drop to zero at the wake debonding strain, ε_{33}^w .

Figures 15 show the longitudinal stress-strain and transverse stress-strain response in the different layers. As can be seen from Figure 15a, the no-pullout curve is triggered in the 0° layer. This is because the 0° layer carries a transverse tensile stress (Figure 15c) before the wake debonding strain is reached. This tensile stress is created by the constraint of the 90° layer, since its stiffness in the 1 direction is much higher than that of the 0° layer. In order to satisfy equilibrium, the transverse stress in the 90° layer (Figure 15d) is a mirror of that given in Figure 15c.

According to this analysis, even though a 0°/90° laminate is only under in-plane uni-axial tension, the no-pullout curve can still be activated. This is different to the stress-strain response of longitudinal straining of a uni-directional tow.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

A computationally efficient FE model has been developed to predict the mechanical behaviour of ceramic matrix composites with strain-induced damage. The effects of different damage modes and their interactions on mechanical behaviour have been considered.

The basic constituent of the FE model is an orthotropic 8-node brick, which forms a homogenised medium of a heterogeneous uni-directional tow. The non-linear longitudinal material properties are discretised to a multi-linear elastic curve. The constitutive equations for orthotropic materials are used to update the stresses for each increment of the analysis. The model is implemented by a commercial FE package, ABAQUS with a user defined subroutine, UMAT.

Multi-axial stress-strain response and degradation of material properties have been modelled for a unidirectional tow, and for a 0°/90° laminate. In all analyses, the expected mechanical behaviour has been obtained. For the 0°/90° laminate under uni-axial straining, the no-pullout stress-strain response in the 0° layer is triggered due to the constraint of the 90° layer.

The high efficiency and the simplicity of the model make it possible to analyse large scale woven composites. Application of the model to unit cells and to real engineering components will be pursued as future developments.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Matthew Blacklock is gratefully acknowledged for providing the material properties used in this paper; and, for ongoing discussions.

References

1. Marshall, D. B. and Cox, B. N. 2008 Integral textile ceramic structures. *Annu. Rev. Mater. Res.*, **38**, 425–443.
2. Sheikh, M. A., Taylor, S. C., Hayhurst, D. R. and Taylor, R. 2001 Microstructural finite element modelling of a ceramic matrix composite to predict experimental measurements of its macro thermal properties. *Model. Simul. Mater. Sci. Eng.* **9**, 7–23.
3. Deepak, G. and Whitcomb, J. D. 2008 Load flow in plain woven composites. *Journal of Composite Materials.* **42**, 2761–2777.
4. Tanov, R. and Tabiei, A. 2001 Computationally efficient micromechanical models for woven fabric composite elastic moduli. *Journal of Applied Mechanics.* **68**, 553–560.
5. Cox, B. N., Carter, W. C., and Fleck, N. A. 1994 A binary model of textile composites—I. Formulation. *Acta Metall. Mater.* **42**, 3463–3479.
6. Hayhurst, D. R., Leckie, F. A. and Evans, A. 1991 Component design-based model for deformation and rupture of tough fibre-reinforced ceramic matrix composites. *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. A.* **434**, 369–381.
7. Tang, C., Blacklock, M, and Hayhurst, D. R. 2008 Thermo-mechanical behaviour of Ceramic Matrix Composites: Part I- Stress-strain response and thermal conductivity degradation of fibre tows. Research report No. DMM. 08.04, School of Mechanical, Aerospace and Civil Engineering, The University of Manchester, U.K.
8. Karandikar, P. and Chou, T. 1993 Characterization and modelling of microcracking and elastic moduli changes in Nicalon/CAS composites. *Composites Science and Technology.* **46**, 253–263.
9. SIMULIA. 2006 ABAQUS user's manual. Version 6.6.
10. Sheikh, M. A., Hayhurst, D.R., Taylor, S. C. and Taylor, R. 2007 Experimental Investigation of the effect of mechanical loading on Thermal Transport in Ceramic Matrix Composites Research report No. DMM. 08.06, School of Mechanical, Aerospace and Civil Engineering, The University of Manchester, U.K.
11. Tang, C., Blacklock, M, and Hayhurst, D. R. 2008 Thermo-mechanical behaviour of Ceramic Matrix Composites: Part II- Stress-strain response and thermal conductivity degradation of fibre tows, 0-90 uni-directional and woven composites. Research report No. DMM. 08.05, School of Mechanical, Aerospace and Civil Engineering, The University of Manchester, U.K.